

Deliverable D 5.3 Demonstrators

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AE	Acoustic Emission
CFRP	Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics
DC ERM	Direct Current Electrical Resistance Measurement
DIC	Digital Image Correlation
EIT	Electrical Impedance Tomography
EMI	Electro-Mechanical Impedance
EoL	End of Life
FBG	Fibre Bragg Gratings
GFRP	Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastics
HPDC	High-Pressure-Die-Cast
KET	Key Enabling Technology
LPBF	Laser Powder Bed Fusion
LPDC	Low-Pressure-Die-Cast
NDI	Non-Destructive Inspection
PVDF	Polyvinylidene Difluoride
PWAS	Piezoelectric Wafer Active Sensors
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SLS	Single Lap Shear
TEP	Thermal Expanding Particles
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UD	Uni-Directional
UGW	Ultrasonic Guided Wave
UT	Ultrasonic Testing

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

SUSTAINair aims to advance the aerospace industry towards the circular economy model. For this purpose, eight key enabling technologies (KETs) were identified that should be developed further. Within SUSTAINAIR, the ambition was to achieve technology readiness level (TRL) 4, by the end of this project. The key enabling technologies identified are:

1. **Design for improved maintenance repair and overhaul (MRO) operations of morphing wing structures**
2. **Online process monitoring of induction and conduction welding of thermoplastic composite structures**
3. **Hybrid recycled laminate materials, enabling highly efficient variable thickness parts**
4. **Improvement of processing conditions in Laser Powder Bed Fusion and powder recycling strategies for enhanced titanium powder life cycles**
5. **Advanced near-net shape manufacturing of nano-eutectic aluminium alloys providing repairable, laser-welded structural assemblies**
6. **Piezo polymer SHM sensors in metallic and polymer parts**
7. **Interface design for dissimilar joints by combination of nano- and macro-structured joint interfaces**
8. **Rivet removal robot heat to dismantle EoL aircraft for maximised recyclate value**

Of these technologies, it was decided that the rivet removal robot would be demonstrated within WP2 due to changes in the consortium make-up, and the fact that rivet removal is more relevant for creating 2nd life material. The other technologies were incorporated into three demonstrators. These three demonstrators served first to validate achieving TRL4 for these technologies. Secondly, the demonstrators can serve as prototypes for further development of the technologies to TRL 9. Thirdly, the demonstrators can be used in disseminating the results of SUSTAINair.

The three demonstrators designed are:

- **Demonstrator I: Wing segment** (main partners: AIT, INO, INVENT, JKU)
This demonstrator incorporates the following KETs: 1 – Design for improved MRO, 5 – Advanced near net-shape manufacturing, and 6 – Piezoelectric polymer sensors
- **Demonstrator II: Hybrid joints** (main partners: DLR, INVENT, JKU)
This demonstrator incorporates the following KETs: 1 – Design for improved MRO, 4 – Improvement of laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) powder reuse and 7 – Interface design for dissimilar joints. It also includes a novel SHM system for hybrid CFRP-Ti joints, developed by JKU.
- **Demonstrator III: Stiffened panel** (main partners: NLR, DTC)
This demonstrator incorporates the following KETs: 2 – Online process monitoring, 3 – Hybrid recycled laminate materials.

This deliverable shows the design of the three demonstrators and provides a high-level evaluation of the obtained testing results for the three demonstrators.

1 INTRODUCTION

The SUSTAINair project has the ambition to advance the aerospace industry's transition to a circular economy model. To achieve this ambition, 8 key enabling technologies (KETs) were identified and further developed within SUSTAINair. In order to advance these technologies to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4, three demonstrators were manufactured and tested. These demonstrators validated the performance of the KETs in representative structures, can serve as prototypes for further development, and can be used to disseminate the results of the SUSTAINair project.

As mentioned, three demonstrators were created. Demonstrator I consists of a wing profile, incorporating advanced metal manufacturing technology, a structural health monitoring (SHM) system and detachable hybrid joints. Demonstrator II consists of hybrid titanium – carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) joints. Demonstrator III consists of a stringer stiffened skin panel incorporating recycled thermoplastic CFRP material.

This document starts by reviewing the design of the three demonstrators, following by a section in which the final manufactured demonstrators are shown, and the final section provides a high-level evaluation of the obtained demonstrator testing results. Report D5.1 (*confidential*) and report D5.2 (*confidential*) provide full details of the demonstrator design and a full assessment of the obtained results.

2 DEMONSTRATORS

2.1 Link KETs and demonstrators

Three demonstrator designs have been developed to demonstrate the seven selected KETs at TRL4. These are:

- Demonstrator I: A wing structure containing an inner aluminium structure joined to a flexible glass fibre reinforced polymer skin.
- Demonstrator II: Hybrid titanium – CFRP joints with nano and macroscale interface design
- Demonstrator III: A thermoplastic stiffened skin panel, incorporating recycled material.

Table 2-1 shows which demonstrator incorporates which KETs. The detailed design of each demonstrator is documented in the following chapters.

Table 2-1: Link between demonstrators and KETs

Demonstrator	KET
Demonstrator I – Wing structure	1 – Design for MRO 5 – Advanced near net-shape manufacturing 6 – Piezoelectric polymer SHM sensors
Demonstrator II – Hybrid joints	1 – Design for MRO 4 – Improvement of LPBF powder recycling 7 – Interface design for dissimilar joints
Demonstrator III – Stiffened panel	2 – Online process monitoring 3 – Hybrid recycled laminate materials

3 DEMONSTRATOR I

3.1 Introduction

Demonstrator I consists of a wing segment which demonstrates the technologies developed in the former work packages. It incorporates 3 of the 8 KETs, namely:

- KET 1** – Design for MRO
- KET 5** – Advanced near net-shape manufacturing
- KET 6** – Piezoelectric polymer SHM sensors

3.2 Design description

The following chapter will give a detailed description of the design of demonstrator I based on the computer aided design (CAD) model shown in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: CAD model of demonstrator I

The leading edge of the wing contains hybrid joints between Fluorine Kautschuk Material (FKM) and thermoset Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastic (GFRP) which can be found, for example, in morphing wing structures. The joints include a functional layer to detach and reattach the joining partners. This improves MRO operations by increasing the reparability of single components. As a result, the service life of the aircraft is extended and dismantling at the end of its service life is simplified.

Two other interfaces of dissimilar joints can be found in the wing segment. Firstly, Thermal Expanding Particles (TEP) are introduced into the adhesive bond between aluminium and GFRP. By heating the bond, the particles expand, make the adhesive brittle, and allow for easy disassembly of the joining partners.

The support structure, namely spars and ribs, is produced from aluminium. Through the creation of nano-eutectic microstructures the material properties of the aluminium alloy are improved. The combination of Low-Pressure-Die-Cast (LPDC) and High-Pressure-Die-Cast (HPDC) components demonstrates the versatility of the deployed alloy. Furthermore, the suitability for

welding is remarkably increased, which greatly reduces the number of fasteners needed for the assembly.

The aluminium spars and ribs are produced by AIT. INVENT produces the GFRP skins and joined them with the aluminium structure. By employing KET6 technology, the wing structure of Demonstrator I can undergo real-time evaluation, a process known as Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). Collaboratively, project partners from JKU, JR, INO, and INVENT work together to create a sensor foil capable of enclosing sensor materials (by JR), contacted by zinc tracks (by INO) to establish connections for data measurement and evaluation (handled by JKU).

3.3 Manufactured demonstrator

3.3.1 Manufacturing of aluminium support structure

Manufacture of the aluminium support structure followed a multi-step and multi-process approach to demonstrate the suitability of the nano-eutectic Al alloy (KET 5, variant SUSair_14.14, AlMg6Si2Zn3FeNi) in three relevant processing conditions:

Manufacture of the aluminium support structure followed a multi-step and multi-process approach to demonstrate the suitability of the nano-eutectic Al alloy (KET 5, variant SUSair_14.14, AlMg6Si2Zn3FeNi) in three relevant processing conditions:

- Castability via High Pressure Die Casting (HPDC, high cooling rate)
- Castability via Low Pressure Die Casting (LPDC, low cooling rate)
- MIG welding (Metal Inert Gas) of cast structural elements

Both spars and ribs were manufactured with 3mm wall thickness, which reflects realistic dimensions in loaded structural assemblies without compromising lightweighting potential. Please find Figure 3-2 for a picture of the CAD design of Demonstrator I and the realized final structure.

Figure 3-2: Left: CAD structural details of DEM I. White lines indicate the position of weld seams in the spar structures. Right: Final assembly of the aluminium support structure with polished weld seams

Spars were manufactured by welding of multiple sections cut out of standard HPDC “cast tubes”. This was an intentional compromise to emphasize the original project scope of “seamless substructures” enabled by the deficiency free welding properties of the KET 5 alloy.

The overall spar manufacturing chain could be evaluated as advanced with respect to the process parameters required both for HPDC and welding, both owing to the comparatively high Magnesium content of the nano-eutectic alloy (~ 6 wt.-%). Nevertheless, stable conditions could be established within industrial boundary conditions, thereby proving the suitability of the alloy for high-throughput production at high quality.

Ribs were manufactured using LPDC into 3D-printed sand forms. Formfilling simulation (not shown) was performed pre ordering the sand forms to validate initial casting temperatures for complete form filling and design of gate, riser and feeder design.

To enable stoichiometrically isotropic weld seams, the welding wire was produced from identical material using LKRs extrusion-based wire manufacturing route.

Wall thickness is 3mm for all aluminium substructures, as formfilling simulation (NovaCast™) indicated a good compromise between form filling under unfavourable conditions (very low melt velocity in sand casting) and desired lightweighting in aerospace structures.

Weld seams were polished manually. No destructive testing was performed on the structure, but visual inspection of polished weld seams

Deviations from the original planning: the interface between the spars, horizontal rib plates and the GFRP laminate was anticipated to be reinforced with MIG welded Al pins from the same alloy. In the layout phase, it was realized that the different coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of aluminium and GFRP would harm the structural integrity of the final demonstrator, as aluminium will expand much stronger than GFRP during the curing process of the laminate. During cooldown aluminium will shrink and introduce internal stresses. Because of the length of the joint (~1000 mm) this will most likely result in destruction of the joint.

Microstructural analysis (not shown here) revealed that no significant deviation in forming of the nano-eutectic phase structure occurred between HPDC and LPDC, despite cooling rates differing by at least a factor 2 (HPDC: >>100 K/s; LPDC <50 K/s). Likewise, weld seams did not exhibit any signs of HAZ (Heat Affected Zones) which leads to weakening in commercial aluminium grades.

3.3.2 Manufacturing of wing skins and wing leading edge

After obtaining the aluminium support structure from AIT-LKR the composite components were produced, and the demonstrator was assembled by INVENT. As a first step, the raw laminates for the wings skins and the leading were manufactured. For the wing skins tooling from a previous research project GRETEL could be reused. For the wing leading edge, a new aluminium tool was machined by INVENT. Glass fibre prepreg was used for all components. Additionally, for the wing leading edge, a scarfed joint between FKM and GFRP was integrated directly during the layup. Furthermore, a thermoplastic interlayer was introduced in the joint interface to enable improved MRO operations. Subsequently the laminates were cured in an autoclave process to get a high laminate quality. As a final step before assembly, the outer surfaces of the laminates were painted using a certified process for civil aircraft parts. The surfaces not to be painted were masked off

and several coats of paint material were applied to ensure an even coating. Figure 3-3 shows the component after the painting was finished.

Figure 3-3: Finished wing leading edge before assembly

In Figure 3-4 another detailed view of the wind leading shows the scarfed joint between GFRP and FKM. The thermoplastic PMMA interlayer developed in WP4 and described in Deliverable D4.1 was uniformly integrated in the laminate layup and is clearly visible from the demonstrator sides.

Figure 3-4: Detailed view of scarfed joint with thermoplastic interlayer

3.3.3 Manufacturing of sensor foil

To enable live monitoring of the joint interfaces a sensor foil was manufactured by INO and JR. Several test layouts with transparent foils, self-adhesive films, electro-spun piezoelectric nanofiber sensor mats and atmospheric pressure plasma deposited conductive zinc lines were evaluated. Top and bottom PET foils were masked, and zinc coated. The Polyvinylidene Difluoride (PVDF) nanofiber mats, manufactured by JR, were placed in cutouts. The mats were spun on A5 size coated paper and formatted by scissors to appropriate size (see Figure 3-5).

Figure 3-5: Electro-spun piezo-electric PVDF nanofiber mat on A5 size coated paper

In Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) cross section images, the structure of the electro-spun nanofiber mats is visible (see Figure 3-6). A high-resolution SEM image of individual fibres with a diameter 0.2 - 0.3 μm is presented in Figure 3-7. After formatting the piezoelectric sensor mats were positioned and joined to a final sensor patch, which is described in detail in Deliverable D5.1. The sensor mats (sandwich design) were manufactured in several stages.

Figure 3-6: Scanning electron microscopy cross section image of PVDF nanofiber mat on paper

Figure 3-7: SEM image of individual electro-spun PVDF fibres

Figure 3-8 shows the initial steps of pre-masking the required foils for the coating process. Steps 1 and 2 illustrate the pre-defined cutting pattern and the unprocessed foil pre-cut to rough dimensions. After the application of the first masking layer on the foil in step 3, the cutting pattern is applied on top in step 4.

After the application of the cutting schematic, the pattern shown in step 5 (Figure 3-9) is cut out and immediately removed, as seen in step 6. Once all cutting steps are completed, the foil is placed on the cooling stage at INO GmbH, ready to be coated under optimal thermal conditions (step 7). The excess masking tape is removed from the fully coated foil, as shown in steps 8 and 9 in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-8: Macro-documentation of sensor foil manufacturing steps, 1 = cutting pattern, 2 = unprocessed foil, 3 = masked foil, 4 = cutting pattern applied on masked foil

Figure 3-9: Macro-documentation of sensor foil manufacturing steps, 5 = cut out pattern, 6 = excessive masking removed, 7 = masked foil placed on cooling stage at INO, 8 = coated foil

To ensure optimal placement of all foil layers, each individual layer is placed in a custom-made clamping device (step 10). Before the double-sided adhesive and the top foils are applied, the JR-made PVDF sensor circles are stamped and placed in a three-stack on each sensor pad (step 11). The final step includes applying the double-sided adhesive (step 12) and the final placement of the top foil.

Figure 3-10: Macro-documentation of sensor foil manufacturing steps, 9 = masking removed from coated foil, 10 = foil placed in clamping device, 11 = layering of PVDF circles, 12 = foil before final adhesive application

Figure 3-11: Final form of sensor foils in 3 versions

The final product of the sensor foils is shown in Figure 3-11. In a final step, the sensor mats were conducted and wired in cooperation of INO and JKU. This is shown in section 3.3.5 in Figure 3-14. Additionally, to emphasize the application, the foil was surrounded with polyimide tape, which had the positive side effect of increasing adhesion to the demonstrator surface, especially to the glass fibre composite. The specific layer-by-layer architecture of the sensor sandwich is displayed in Deliverable D5.1 under section 3.2. The assembled sensor patch, same as the manufactured Demonstrator 1, was transferred to JKU and installed by INO and JKU inside Demonstrator 1. The specialized connector plug enabled further functionality testing by JKU.

3.3.4 Assembly Demonstrator I

In the next and final step all parts were assembled by adhesively bonding the composite parts to the aluminium frame. Figure 3-12 shows the demonstrator during the assembly process. The composite components were aligned, fixed and bonded to the supporting structure one after the other.

Figure 3-12: Composite components and aluminium support structure during assembly

3.3.5 Test Setup

Demonstrator I was equipped with the sensor foil (from JR and INO) at JKU and measurements were carried out without structural load. The aim of the test was to determine whether the conductive paths of the flexible foil work and whether a signal can be detected with the new type of fiber sensors. The setup at JKU is shown in Figure 3-13 and the applied sensor foil inside Demonstrator I, placed above the glass fiber composite / aluminum joint, is shown in Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-13: Overview of test setup for Demonstrator I at JKU

Figure 3-14: Applied sensor foil inside Demonstrator I with contacting by flat ribbon cable

The test setup consists of the SHM system, which in this configuration can perform measurements for the acoustic methods Electro-mechanical Impedance (EMI) and Ultrasonic Guided Wave (UGW). Since 4 conventional piezoelectric transducers and 4 novel nanofiber sensors were used on the sensor mat, the SHM system is configured for measurements with 8 sensors. Figure 3-14, together with Figure 3-15 explain the layout, numbering and location of the specific sensor types used. The equipment list is found in Table 3-1.

Figure 3-15: Schematic top view of the applied sensor foil inside Demonstrator I. Numbering, sensor material (piezoceramic PWAS or PVDF) and substrate (GFRP or aluminium) is indicated.

Table 3-1: Equipment list for the SHM measurement system (laboratory setup)

Instruments used and name	SHM method
2x 4-channel oscilloscope (Tektronix DPO2004B)	UGW
1x function generator (Tektronix AFG3022C)	
1x impedance analyzer (Hioki IM3570)	EMI
1x switch unit (self-designed; MATLAB controlled)	all methods
1x data acquisition PCs	all methods

4 DEMONSTRATOR II

4.1 Introduction

Demonstrator II represents a typical aircraft structure commonly found in crash structures of the lower fuselage of passenger airplanes, where titanium is used to increase the strength of the structure. It consists of a hybrid joint between titanium and CFRP material. Demonstrator II incorporates 3 of the 8 KETs described in Chapter 2.

The following KETs are addressed:

- KET 1** – Design for improved MRO operations of morphing wing structures
- KET 4** – Improvement of LPBF powder recycling
- KET 7** – Interface design for dissimilar joints

4.2 Design description

An overview of the demonstrator is shown in Figure 4-1. The demonstrator consists of one additively manufactured titanium bracket in an L-shape and two carbon fibre-reinforced composite plates, which are individually co-bonded with the titanium bracket. The main focus lies on the pinned joint, which is similar to the pinned hybrid joint developed in WP4 and investigated for SHM methods in WP3. The second joint is a detachable joint, realized to accomplish KET 1 in this demonstrator design.

The overall dimensions of the demonstrator are (length x width x height): 350 x 101.6 x 55 mm³.

Figure 4-1: CAD model of Demonstrator II. Sensor locations are not final. Sensors located on the other side and electrical contacts are not shown.

4.3 Manufactured demonstrator

4.3.1 Manufacturing of titanium bracket

The Ti6Al4V brackets of the joining demonstrators were additively manufactured using the powder bed fusion, laser-based metal process (PBF-LB/M) on the SLM 280^{HL} setup at DLR. The process was carried out in Argon atmosphere at a build platform temperature of 200 °C using the process parameters developed in WP2. As feedstock, the recycled 2nd life powder was employed. For the pins the geometry Spike 5 (height 1.8 mm, diameter 0.5 mm) is chosen based on the results from WP4. The pins were arranged with a distance of 4 mm in both axis to cover the whole joining area symmetrically (Figure 4-2).

Figure 4-2: PBF-LB/M manufacturing preparation for bracket build with 5 x 25 Spike 5 pin pattern

After additive manufacturing of the titanium bracket, it was machined on INVENT's premises. The rough surface – a residue of the manufacturing process – was milled down. For this purpose, a machining offset was accounted for during the design phase. Moreover, the holes for the clamping in the testing jig were milled. The angle between the pin surface and the clamping should be 90°. To achieve this value, it was not possible to mill away the entire machining offset. After machining the surface of the joining interface laser treated by DLR.

Figure 4-3: PBF-LB/M printed Titanium bracket after machining.

The final step before the actual joining procedure consisted of the pulsed laser pretreatment carried out at DLR after machining at Invent. The laser pretreatment process employed in WP4 was transferred to the demonstrator stage for this purpose and the entire joining zone pretreated with a single laser scan repetition using parameters optimized previously with the single-lap shear samples in WP4. The Cleanlaser CL20 setup was used again on air after cleaning the machined demonstrators using isopropanol and acetone in two subsequent steps in an ultrasonic bath. The pins present on the joining zone were not affected since they were out of the laser focus distance set to the level plane of the joint.

4.3.2 Manufacturing of detachable joint laminate

For the manufacturing of the detachable joint laminate by INVENT the same design approach as for the functional interlayer described in section 3.3.2 were followed. A thermoplastic interlayer was co-cured with a laminate in the autoclave to form a joint interface that is detachable by heating. The laminate itself was made from CFRP prepreg. The functional interlayer was introduced as a last layer to the layup. The final product can be seen in Figure 4-4.

Figure 4-4: Detachable joint laminate before bonding to demonstrator

4.3.3 Assembly of Demonstrator II

In a first step for the assembly of Demonstrator II the CFRP prepreg material must be co-bonded to the pin interface. In this co-bonding process, the uncured thermoset resin of the pre-impregnated CFRP prepreg material bonds directly with the prefabricated titanium bracket. A special pressing device was produced for this process. This jig is shown in Figure 4-5.

The jig has a bottom part to fit the pre-machined titanium bracket. The upper part leaves only the pin interface of the titanium bracket accessible. Carbon fibre fabric prepreg material was placed inside the mould and cured directly on the pin interface. The semi-finished part after demoulding is shown in Figure 4-6.

The semi-finished part was trimmed, and excessive resin was manually removed. In the last step the detachable joint laminate was bonded to the demonstrator. No autoclave process was used in this step to apply temperature and pressure. Instead, the laminate was aligned and pressured by a weight. In the last step GFRP-steel tabs were adhesively bonded to the demonstrator. The final products are shown in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-5: Press jig for co-bonding of CFRP and titanium bracket

Figure 4-6: Semi-finished demonstrator after co-bonding process.

Figure 4-7: Demonstrator II before quality assurance and shipping to JKU for instrumentation and testing

5 DEMONSTRATOR III

5.1 Introduction

Thermoplastics offer great potential due to their ability to be remelted multiple times which can be vastly beneficial for recycling and welding for example. Traditionally skin stiffened structures on an airplane like a fuselage, rudders, ailerons and wing skins feature bolted stiffeners, even for thermoset structures, due to the certification challenges associated with bonding. Welding can overcome these challenges and furthermore offers good potential for reduced (assembly) time and costs, lower weight, improved inspections and better recycling potential. Challenges with welding are online process monitoring and control and the high processing temperatures for thermoplastics like PPS, PEKK and LM-PAEK.

The selected KETs for Demonstrator III are addressing the challenges of online process monitoring and also focus on the use of recycled materials. An overview of the selected KETs and manufacturing processes are shown below. They were selected based on the obtained results from work package 4.

The following KETs are addressed:

KET 2 – Online process monitoring of induction and conduction welding of thermoplastic composite structures

KET 3 – Hybrid recycled laminate materials, enabling highly efficient variable thickness parts

5.2 Design description

A skin stiffened fuselage or wing skin was taken as a reference for the design of Demonstrator III. It featured a single curved skin of constant thickness, on which multiple rows of L-stiffeners were attached through induction welding. The length of the L-stiffeners is different, to demonstrate the potential of continuous induction welding of long stiffeners. It also makes the demonstrator more representative, as stiffeners are normally not continuous along the entire fuselage length or wingspan. This is because ribs and frames can run across, or stiffening elements around doors, inspection holes and windows are present.

A CAD picture and a photo of the actual demonstrator are shown in Figure 5-1, more detailed information on manufacturing and evaluation can be found in the next sections. The size of the skin is 1900 x 600 mm with a radius of 2538.3 mm. Two different lengths are used for the L-stiffeners. The shorter stiffeners have a length of 550 mm and are made from a combination of 1st and 2nd life Toray Cetex® TC1100 T300/PPS fabric with a thickness of approximately 2.2 mm. The long stiffeners and the skin are made from 1st life Toray Cetex® TC1225 T700/LM-PAEK Uni-Directional (UD) tape and the stiffeners have a length of 1230 mm, and a thickness of 2.2 mm. Stiffener pitch is 212 mm.

Figure 5-1: Design of Demonstrator III

5.3 Manufactured demonstrator

Multiple manufacturing processes were used to manufacture the demonstrator. Below an overview is given.

- Automated fibre placement of the skin
- Autoclave consolidation of the skin
- Recycling of thermoplastics (2nd life) for 2nd life PPS Ls-stiffeners
- Press forming of the L-profiles
- Induction welding

Partners involved are DTC Collins and NLR. DTC Collins provided press formed L-stiffeners to NLR in 1st life (T700 LM-PAEK) and 2nd life (T300/PPS) material. NLR manufactured a single curved panel on which the L-stiffeners are assembled using induction welding. Two online monitoring techniques are used to measure the interface temperatures during welding.

5.3.1 Manufacturing of the skin

5.3.1.1 Automated fibre placement of the skin

The skin is made from T700/LM-PAEK (stage 2) UD tapes and has a constant thickness of 2.2 mm. A Coriolis Fibre Placement Robot at NLR was used to simultaneously place 8 UD tapes of 6.35 mm width on a curved tool, see Figure 5-2, to manufacture the skin. A 6 kW laser is used to heat the skin and the tapes which are placed on the skin.

Figure 5-2: Fibre placement of demonstrator skin

5.3.1.2 Autoclave consolidation of the skin

After fibre placement the skin is consolidated in the autoclave. High temperature consumables like polyimide foil, sealant tape and breather materials are needed to withstand the process temperature of 365 °C. Pictures of the different steps during the construction of the autoclave package are shown in Figure 5-3. A carbon/polyimide slip sheet was placed between the tool and the skin to compensate the different thermal expansion properties of the tool and the skin (see top left picture in Figure 5-3). The skin was consolidated at 365 °C at 7 bar overpressure and full vacuum according to the standard process recommendations of Toray.

Figure 5-3: Construction of autoclave package for consolidation of the skin

5.3.2 Recycling of thermoplastics for 2nd life PPS L-stiffeners

For the manufacturing of the 2nd-life CF/PPS laminates, shredded material with irregular size and geometry was used. The shredded 2nd life material is spread on a layer of 1st life fabric-based CF/PPS material and covered with another layer of 1st life fabric-based CF/PPS. The lay-up is then consolidated into a solid laminate. Please find Figure 54 for a picture showing the shredded material used as an input for the 2nd life laminate. The laminates produced have an average thickness of 2,25 mm, consisting of 2 x 0,3 mm 1st life material facings and 1,65 mm of 2nd life core material.

After consolidation NDI scans of the fabricated laminates were made, using ultrasonic equipment. A representative image of the outcome of such scan can be seen in Figure 5-5.

Figure 5-4: Shredded material used as input for the 2nd life CF/PPS laminate

Figure 5-5: NDI scan of 2nd life CF/PPS laminate

5.3.3 Press-forming of the L-profiles

The stamp forming mould shown in Figure 5-6 with a length of 1300 mm was constructed and manufactured, to enable the forming of the long 1st life LMPAEK/T700 and the 2nd life PPS/T300 stiffeners.

Figure 5-6: Model of stamp forming tool (negative side) with formed component

The L-profiles have been formed using 1st life CF/LM-PAEK material as well as 2nd life CF/PPS material, with the standard stamp forming process at Collins Aerospace DTC. The profile length as stamp formed is 1300 mm and the profiles have been cut to the specified length, e.g. 1230 mm for the 1st life LMPAEK/T700 UD tape material and 550 mm for the 2nd life PPS/T300 fabric, both

with a thickness of approximately 2.2 mm. The long stiffeners have also been provided with a narrow 0,75 mm groove, enabling the enclosure of optical fibres for online monitoring. Details of the manufactured profiles can be seen in Figure 5-7.

a) Detail of groove in 1230 mm long L-profile

b) Picture of 550 mm long 2nd life CF/PPS L-Profile

Figure 5-7: Detailed view of manufactured Profile

NDI inspection of the formed parts was performed using phased array ultrasonic scanning, as shown in Figure 5-8. Clearly the results for the 1st life material are more homogeneous and on average on a higher level (red indicates perfectly consolidated laminate, light blue indicates a high level of porosity). The quality of the stamp formed 2nd life profile seems to be somewhat better than the flat laminate of which it was produced, and the results point to a well consolidated 2nd life product, taking into account the characteristics of the recycled material in terms of fibre length distribution and fibre angle within the laminate.

Figure 5-8: Picture of C-scan results for 1st life CF/LMPAEK (left) and 2nd life CF/PPS L-profile (right)

5.3.4 Assembly of Demonstrator III

At NLR the induction welding robot featuring a 10kW Ambrell power supply and standardized KVE induction coil shown in Figure 5-9 was used to weld the long 1st life LM-PAEK/T700 and the 2nd life PPS/T300 stiffeners on the skin. A new weld setup and tool was developed and manufactured to perform the welding. The maximum simultaneous weld length is 1000 mm but the setup is designed in such a way that it is possible to sequentially weld multiple sections of a 1000 mm by moving the product through the setup. In theory the weld length is infinite.

Figure 5-9: Induction welding robot and weld tooling for the Demonstrator III

First, the L-stiffener is placed in the lower tooling. Next, the curved skin is placed on top of the L-stiffener and the assembly is placed below the upper tooling. A high temperature composite heatsink is part of the upper tooling to prevent overheating of the skin during welding. The induction coil is moved through a groove in the upper tooling and runs along the heatsink. During welding, pressure at the weld interface is applied by an air pressurized silicone pressure bellow which is located beneath the L-profile. After welding the L-stiffener is allowed to cool down under pressure to below 100 °C. The target temperature during welding was 340 or 360 °C at a pressure of 6 bar depending on the type of stiffener. Once a L-stiffener is fully welded the skin is removed from the setup and the same procedure is repeated for the next stiffener. In case of a sequential weld, the skin with the partially welded L-stiffener is shifted to its new position in the tooling after which the second section is welded. An overlap of 100 mm between the two weld sections is applied to achieve a high-quality weld of constant width.

All L-stiffeners were welded using a standardized weld protocol. A so-called power curve weld is performed in which several thermocouples are placed at the weld interface. During the power curve weld, multiple runs at increasing current are performed to determine the temperature at the settings. The welding speed is fixed. The final current needed to reach the target temperature is predicted based on an extrapolation of the test data and verified with an actual weld at this current. Pictures of the different steps during welding are shown in Figure 5-10.

Placement of small L-stiffener in lower tool

Placement of skin on L-stiffener and lower tool

Figure 5-10: Welding of L-stiffeners on skin

Two online monitoring techniques were used to measure the interface temperatures during welding. The first is Type E thermocouples and is the baseline measurements technique. The second technique is an optical fibre with Fibre Bragg Gratings (FBG) which is one of the KETs evaluated within this demonstrator. On two of the three long LM-PAEK/T700 stiffeners an optical fibre was used to measure the temperature during welding. The outcome is described in a next section. On the third LM-PAEK stiffener and on the three 2nd life L-stiffeners thermocouples were used. Figure 5-11 show the order in which the stiffeners were welded, stiffeners 1, 5 and 6 are the 1st life LM-PAEK stiffeners and 2, 3 and 4 are the 2nd life PPS stiffeners. Stiffeners 2 and 3 were welded from the outside of the skin toward the middle, stiffener 4 was welded from the middle of the skin toward the edge due to the design of the weld setup.

Figure 5-11: Welding order of L-stiffeners on skin

5.3.4.1 Welding of 2nd life T300/PPS stiffeners

Six thermocouples were used during welding of the PPS stiffeners to directly measure the temperature at the weld interface, see Figure 5-12 for the positions of the thermocouples. To improve the temperature development at the start of the weld a 5 second dwell was given before the induction coil was further translated over the demonstrator. For the PPS stiffeners, the middle stiffener was welded first as this will be used as alignment for positioning and welding of the outer two stiffeners.

Figure 5-12: Thermocouples positions during welding of PPS L-stiffeners

To get a better understanding of the temperature development three runs were done at low current. Using this data the final current needed to weld the parts could be determined. Temperature measurements of the one to last and of the final weld run of the middle stiffener are shown in Figure 5-13.

Figure 5-13: Temperature measurements during welding of 2nd life PSS/T300 stiffener

During the final run the average temperature was 332 °C, slightly below the target temperature of 340 °C. Also some variation between the different thermocouples is present. This is inherent with the induction welding process and is increased due to the irregular (micro)structure of the shredded 2nd life material in the stiffener. A similar behaviour was found during welding of the coupons in WP4. During welding of the two other 2nd life PPS stiffener only the first, third and sixth thermocouples were used as the achieved temperatures matched the ones from the first stiffener within 5 °C. The target temperature for these two stiffeners was set at 350 °C and 360 °C at 6 bar and 7 bar pressure respectively to investigate if it would affect the quality determined by C-scan (see section 6.3). The actual average temperature achieved during welding of the two outer stiffeners was 350.6 °C and 360.0 °C respectively with a maximum variation between the three thermocouples of +/- 5°C from the average.

5.3.4.2 Welding of 1st life T700/LM-PAEK stiffeners

Due to the length of the LM-PAEK stiffeners welding was performed in two steps to join the stiffeners across the entire length of 1230 mm. Only at the start of the first section a dwell of 5 seconds at the specified current was performed. During welding of the second section the dwell was not applied and an overlap of 100 mm was used with the first section, see Figure 5-14 for a graphical overview. Welding strategy for run 6 was the same as for run 1, run 5 was welded from skin edge to the middle of the skin due to the design of the weld setup. The weld length of the 1st section is 850 mm of the second section the length is 480 mm.

Figure 5-14: Weld strategy of 1st life T700/LM-PAEK stiffeners

Temperature measurements for the middle stiffener were done only with thermocouples. In case of the two outer stiffeners a combination of thermocouples and an optical fibre with FBG’s was used. The thermocouples can be used as a reference for the measured temperature by the FBG’s. As the FBG’s measure strain caused by the thermal expansion of the optical fibre a reference is needed to more accurately convert the strain into temperature. To prevent an effect of mechanical strain on the measurement the optical fibres were placed inside a small quartz capillary. During the research performed in WP4 it was found that the capillary has to be placed in a small groove (0.5 x 0.5 mm) to prevent it from crushing when the welding pressure is applied.

Thermocouple positions during welding of the middle stiffener are shown in Figure 5-15. TC1 until TC6 are entirely in the first weld section. TC7 is precisely at the end of the 1st section (850 mm) and is also part of the 2nd weld section (100 mm from the start of section 2). The average weld temperature of section 1 was 350 °C and of section 2 the average temperature was 367 °C.

Figure 5-15: Thermocouple positioning of middle 1st life T700/LM-PAEK stiffener

For stiffener/run 5 an optical fibre with 5 FBG's was placed in the first section of the weld. Four FBG's were used for temperature measurements and were covered with a capillary. For verification of the FBG's measurement two thermocouples were placed at 600 mm and 800 mm from the start of the weld. One FBG, in this case the fourth, was not covered with the capillary so this could be used for strain measurements. By doing this it could potentially be used for structural health monitoring purposes in actual parts while the other FBG's can be used for temperature measurements during welding.

During welding of the first section the temperature measured by the thermocouples was 354 and 369 °C respectively. Below in Figure 5-16 a comparison between the temperature measured by the 4 FBG's and the two thermocouples is shown for four weld runs at different currents. For a better comparison the FBG data was translated in time to match with the first thermocouple as this was the closest to the FBG's. As can be seen the converted data from the FBG measurements show a good match with the temperature measurements from the two thermocouples. There is some variation between the different FBG's but this is also common when using thermocouples as can also be seen in the graphs. Overall, the test showed it is feasible to use an optical fibre for temperature measurements during induction welding. Further improvements can be made by calibration of each separate FBG in an oven. In this case the calibration was done during the welding process by taking the first thermocouple as a reference. Ideally, each FBG can be calibrated with the same calibration curve but further research is needed to determine the feasibility and acquired accuracy.

Figure 5-16: Comparison of temperature measurements by thermocouples (TC1, TC2) and by optical fibre (FBG1 – FBG3, FBG5. FBG4 only for strain measurements) at different weld current for stiffener 5

During welding of the second section only thermocouples were used and the average temperature was 350 °C.

For stiffener/run 6 an optical fibre with 4 FBG’s was placed in the second section of the weld. The reason for placing it in the second section was better accessibility of the optical fibre connection in the weld tool as this is near the edge of the skin. In this case the entire fibre was placed inside the capillary as the (secondary) goal of this test was to remove the fibre after welding so it could be reused. As FBG’s are relative expensive this could make them more attractive to use for temperature measurements during, in this case, welding. FBG are approximately at 280, 220, 140 and 100 mm from the end of the stiffener. TC’s are at 370 and 550 mm from the end of the stiffener.

In the first weld section thermocouples were located at 100, 300, 670 and 800 mm from the edge of the stiffener. The average temperature during the final weld run of the first three thermocouples was 334 °C which is on the low end but still sufficient to melt the LM-PAEK. In the second section the average weld temperature was approximately 350 °C. Below the comparison between the thermocouple and the FBG measurements is shown for the sixth stiffener. The same calibration curve as for the fifth stiffener was used to convert the FBG strain measurements to a temperature. Again, a good match between the TC and FBG measurements was found with even lower variation between the FBG’s, see Figure 5-17. Only FBG1 shows a larger difference but this is because it is located close to the edge of the stiffener. The weld process was not optimized to fully weld the stiffener and therefore the temperature is lower than the others. FBG2 shows a sharper transition at peak temperature than the other FBG’s, further research would be needed to determine and explain the cause. After welding the optical fibre could be removed from the demonstrator without any damage. This also shows that the capillary is able to withstand the temperature and pressure during induction welding.

Figure 5-17: Comparison of temperature measurements by thermocouples (TC) and by optical fibre (FBG1 – FBG4) at different weld current for stiffener 6

6 TESTING RESULTS EVALUATION

6.1 Demonstrator 1

For details on the individual SHM methods and their basics, please refer to the section 6.2 on testing of Demonstrator II.

The impedance curves of all 8 sensors required for potential EMI applications are shown in Figure 6-1. The respective sensor with its material (piezoceramic or PVDF) and substrate (GFRP or aluminum) is indicated in the legend. Two PVDF sensors (no. 3 and no. 7) have no contact with the substrate due to no attachment of the sensor foil to the demonstrator. However, capacitive behavior could be determined. Whether this behavior originates from the zinc contacts or from the PVDF material itself was not investigated in detail. Piezo no. 1 shows a characteristic impedance curve with a resonance frequency at 233 kHz. The other Piezos no. 4, 5 and 6 do not show this behavior. In this case, it is an indicator of potentially little to poor bonding of Piezo no. 1 to the GFRP substrate. Although this circumstance has no effect in this experiment, it is undesirable. Nevertheless, the evaluation shows that sensor self-diagnosis is also possible with the aid of EMI impedance spectra [Chapter 7, V. Giurgiutiu, Structural Health Monitoring with Piezoelectric Wafer Active Sensors, 2nd edition. Elsevier,2014.].

Figure 6-1: Impedance curves of all 8 sensors integrated in the sensor foil of Demonstrator I. Top: Piezoceramic sensors. Bottom: Novel PVDF sensors

The sensor voltage signals required for potential UGW measurements are shown as an example in Figure 6-2. In this figure, a piezoceramic sensor (Piezo 5) serves as the emitter of an excitation signal, while the other 7 sensors serve as receivers. (The excitation signal – highlighted in blue - is contained in each voltage signal due to inductive transmission of the excitation signal within the switching unit. The actual received signal comes later). Since PVDF sensor 3 and 7 have no surface contact, it is expected that no signal was sensed after excitation of the structure.

However, PVDF sensor 2 and 8 have surface contact, but their signal strength was not able to be detected in a satisfactory way by the instrument setup used. Further investigations with more sensitive readout could provide more precise information about, e.g., the signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 6-2: Sensor signals recorded from Sensor 1 to 4, and 6 to 8, with sensor 5 as excitation signal emitter. Signal highlighted in blue is due to inductive transmission of the excitation signal in the cabling.

The objectives of the experiment were achieved. On the one hand, the functionality of the developed sensor foil and its electrical conductor paths made of deposited zinc is given, because the four conventional sensors were successfully controlled by the SHM system. On the other hand, the novel sensors made of piezoelectric, electro spun polymer were partially suitable for measurements with the current SHM system. The reasons for this could be the weak adhesive layer of the sensor foil to the demonstrator surface and the potentially insufficient bonding/contacting of the contact surfaces between the sensor foil and the fibre material itself. It is suggested that further tests with different measurement equipment are needed.

6.2 Demonstrator 2

The sample preparation is similar to that from WP3 for the tests on the pinned hybrid SLS joint samples. The necessary sensors were attached to the demonstrator and the necessary electrodes were created. These include six piezoelectric transducers, three are attached to the titanium bracket and three to the carbon fibre-reinforced joining partner. These transducers are used for the EMI, UGW and Acoustic Emissions (AE) methods. In addition, eight electrodes were created directly on the composite surface using the laser engraving technique described in [Dengg et al.]^[1]. The exposed conductive carbon fibres were contacted for the method of Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT). One fully prepared Demonstrator II specimen can be seen in Figure 6-3. In the figure, the right lateral side of the specimen’s pinned hybrid joint is covered with a high contrast speckle pattern for DIC evaluation.

Figure 6-3: Exemplary sensor setup shown at Demonstrator II no.5

The test setup, carried out at JKU, includes both its SHM test scope and the structural test scope. For the SHM test scope, the necessary SHM measurement system developed in WP3 by JKU was extended even further and used for the structural tests with Demonstrator II. For this purpose, the method of DC ERM (Direct Current Electrical Resistance Measurement) was extended to another SHM method (EIT) and to a total of 6 piezoelectric transducers (before: 3). For the structural test scope, various preparations precede the tests on Demonstrator II. Both Demonstrator II and the necessary fixture for clamping on the test bench were developed by JKU with the help of an FE analysis and partners DLR and INVENT. The steel fixture for clamping was manufactured by INVENT and sent to JKU. The demonstrators were manufactured to specification by DLR and INVENT. The structural test setup further includes scientific equipment for DIC (Digital Image Correlation) and UT (Ultrasonic Testing).

Three of those specimens were tested identically on the test rig of JKU by multiple cycles of quasi-static loading and unloading to a specified reference load (load controlled). An overall picture of the complete test setup for Demonstrator II can be seen in Figure 6-4.

Figure 6-4: Overview shot of test rig setup for Demonstrator II at JKU

The structural test is performed, with parallel use of SHM methods and is subdivided as follows, based on Deliverable D3.3. On the one hand, the SHM methods EMI, UGW and EIT are recorded at a defined load level on the demonstrator. On the other hand, the AE method is used during loading. The schematic description of the structural loading procedure and SHM method deployment is shown in Figure 6-5. The maximum load of every cycle is continuously increased by 5kN.

Figure 6-5: Schematic description of the structural loading procedure and corresponding SHM methods deployed

For AE, it can be seen that for demonstrator II no. 2, hits were already registered at relatively low load levels such as 5kN, whereas for demonstrator II no. 3 and no. 4, the first hits were registered at a load cycle of 15kN. For all demonstrators tested, significant activity (both in terms of hit count and energy released) can be observed during all higher loads above 15kN. This suggests that the structural loading has an influence on the joining area starting from at least 15kN onwards.

Regarding the EMI method, an impedance spectrum in the range of 210-315 kHz was measured for each piezoelectric sensor. Four such measurement procedures were carried out before the test started and served as reference for the sample’s undamaged state. An EMI measurement procedure follows between each load cycle. Each impedance spectrum is numerically reduced to one value using the statistical metrics RMSD, MAPD and CCD (cf.: D1.1) and compared with the value before the start of the test.

With regard to the UGW method, the "pitch-catch" procedure was used (please refer to D1.1 and D3.3): For this measurement procedure, one piezoelectric sensor at a time acts as the emitter of a burst signal, which is picked up by all remaining sensors on the structure. The recorded voltage signals are numerically processed into CC metrics after each load cycle in comparison with the reference signals recorded before the start of the test. A deviation from 1 indicates a change in the transfer properties and thus potential structural damage.

For Demonstrator II, within the framework of WP5 and WP3, the step was taken from the coupon level (SLS-specimen) to the component level. Although it is a similar pinned overlap made of titanium and CFRP compared to the SLS-specimen in WP3, the clamping conditions result in slightly different shear stress distribution the overlap area. However, this discrepancy was planned to further investigate the dominant damage mode of debonding at the overlap end and an attempt was made to capture it using the SHM methods developed in WP3. This was achieved

with the existing methods. Further, compared to the structural tests from D3.3, the instrumentation was adapted and supplemented with the EIT method.

In summary, with the help of the development and exploration of all defined objectives in WP3, a comprehensive structural test including an extensive SHM measurement concept was demonstrated using Demonstrator II. This setup worked at component level in WP5, so the findings from different WPs were further developed on the demonstrators.

For the demonstration of the SHM system on the component level, a comprehensive measurement data set (US NDE, CT, EIT) was generated, which is also very valuable for future research on advancing damage evaluation methods towards damage localization and quantification.

6.3 Demonstrator 3

There was no significant testing campaign foreseen for Demonstrator III. However, the quality of the welded stiffeners was determined by C-scan and manual loading was applied to the demonstrator to check the functionality of the embedded optical fibre and FBG's in stiffener 5. Also, the optical fibre which was removed after welding of stiffener 6 was reinserted in the capillary again to check if it would respond to any mechanical deformations.

Ultrasonic C-scanning using a squirter method was performed on the skin and weld interface to determine the quality of the demonstrator. For the stiffener webs an immersion method was applied in which the panel is fully immersed in a water tank. The reason for the different methods is that the panel was too large to fully immerse it in the water tank so the only option to inspect the skins and weld interface was using the squirter method. A picture of the inspection setup can be found in Figure 6-6. As the skin is single curved the contour was programmed in the C-scan machine to guarantee that the ultrasonic transducer is perpendicular to the surface of the skin.

Figure 6-6: C-scan inspection setup for demonstrator III

The attenuation scan of the skin is shown in Figure 6-7. It is a measure of the loss of signal which has been transmitted and received by the transducer. In case of low quality due to voids or delaminations more signal is lost and is plotted in a graphical representation. Using the 16 colour palette shown in Figure 6-7 red is an indication of good quality whereas green, blue or black indicate a higher loss of the ultrasonic signal due to the aforementioned quality issues. Evaluating the attenuation scan of the skin

Figure 6-7: Attenuation C-scan of the skin for demonstrator III

The attenuation scan of the weld interfaces of the six L-stiffeners is shown in Figure 6-8. On the left, the short 2nd life PPS stiffeners are shown which give an irregular and scattered pattern. This is due to the discontinuous nature of the 2nd life material which deflects the ultrasonic signal to different directions and thus increasing the loss of signal. It therefore shows a higher attenuation which was also found during inspection of the welded samples in WP4. In this case it makes it hard to determine the quality of the weld interface for the 2nd life PPS stiffeners but it is clear that the upper left L-stiffener which was welded at 7 bar pressure (instead of 6 bar) has a more uniform width compared to the other two stiffeners.

On the right side in Figure 6-8 the results for the three long 1st life LM-PAEK stiffeners is shown. The quality of the weld interface on all three stiffeners is of good quality. Only on the two outer stiffeners a horizontal yellow line is visible which is due to the groove and capillary surrounding the optical fibre. Inside the capillary air is present which gives higher attenuation compared to defect free composite material. The narrow vertical areas in the weld interfaces for both the 2nd life PPS and 1st life LM-PAEK stiffeners are the locations in which the thermocouples were placed. After welding the thermocouples were removed leaving a gap between the skin and the stiffener. This causes a high attenuation loss in these locations and are therefore not taken into account to determine the weld quality. It also shows that using thermocouples in the welding process has a higher impact than using optical fibres.

Figure 6-8: Attenuation C-scan of the weld interfaces for demonstrator III

The C-scan results of the stiffener webs are shown in Figure 6-9. Again a similar effect of the 2nd life material is visible on the PPS stiffener on the right. The 1st life LM-PAEK stiffener on the left show a very constant and high quality web. This indicates that the C-scan results of the weld interfaces are not affected by the quality of the press-formed L-stiffeners (only due to the 2nd life material) and that the induction welding process did not cause any quality issues in the stiffener webs.

Attenuation C-scan of Web 1st life LM-PAEK stiffener 5 (left) and 2nd life PPS stiffener 4 (right)

Attenuation C-scan of Web 1st life LM-PAEK stiffener 1 (left) and 2nd life PPS stiffener 2 (right)

Attenuation C-scan of Web 1st life LM-PAEK stiffener 6 (left) and 2nd life PPS stiffener 3 (right)

Figure 6-9: Attenuation C-scan of the stiffener webs for demonstrator III

A final functional check was done by manually applying a torsional and bending load in the demonstrator to check for any response of the FBG's. In theory, only FBG 4 in stiffener 5 should measure a (small) strain as it was not covered with a capillary. All other FBG's should not show any signal as they are decoupled from mechanical strains by the capillary. In reality all 5 FBG's embedded in stiffener 5 show a signal when the load was applied, see Figure 6-10. It is not sure why this is the case but it could be due to a crushed capillary or due to constraint on the fibre ends as the results of a shifted or local crushed capillary. Further research and inspection would be required to determine the exact cause but was out of the scope of the project.

Figure 6-10: Strain measurement of FBG's in stiffener 5 after applying manual loading

After reinserting the optical fibre in the capillary in stiffener 6 no signals were measured by any of the 4 FBG's after applying the load. In this case it can be concluded that the capillary is intact and is still able to decouple the optical fibre from the applied deformation.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The SUSTAINair consortium has successfully completed the design and manufacturing of three demonstrators, which serve to validate the attainment of TRL 4 for the key enabling technologies for more sustainable aircraft structures identified in the SUSTAINair project. Furthermore, the demonstrators can be used for communication and dissemination activities, both during the remainder of the project or after it has finished.

Demonstrator I successfully demonstrated the use of KET 1, 5 and 6 in the form of a wing segment with an integrated SHM system. The functionality of multiple developed SHM methods could be shown, with promising results, especially for methods based on EMI and UGW (KET 6). No deviations were found during the manufacturing of the repair-friendly morphing joint that enabled detachability through the integrated thermoplastic, functional interlayer (KET 1). The second detachable bond using TEPs also did not lead to non-compliance and demonstrated the scalability of the technology to larger bonding areas. The manufacturing of the aluminium support structure gave valuable insights into primary moulding processing techniques such as LDPC and HPDC (KET 5) as well as subsequent joinability through MIG welding. All used technologies proved to be sufficient. Nonetheless, further research is needed to scale the HPDC process to commercial throughput rates, such as those commonly found in the automotive industry, to establish a more robust processing window. Secondly, the different CTEs of aluminium and thermoset GFRP showed the limits of the current co-bonding process. Further research is therefore needed to identify new design principles that will allow the technology to be scaled up to larger bonding surfaces. Likewise, the manufacturing process for electro spun nanofibers (KET 6) needs additional work to be upscaled to surface areas larger than DIN A5. All in all, demonstrator I gave an ambitious first outlook on the upscaling of the respective KETs to even higher TRL than 4.

Demonstrator II represents a typical aircraft structure commonly found in crash structures of the lower fuselage of passenger airplanes, where titanium is used to increase the strength of the structure. It exhibited the application of KET 1, 4, 7 on a more complex level than coupon testing. The focus of the demonstrator was on the quantitative evaluation of the co-bonded dissimilar joint between thermoset CFRP and additive manufactured titanium components by quasi-static and cyclic loading tests. To enable a statistical evaluation, a total of 5 demonstrators were produced. Besides the mechanical characterisation of the bond strength, extensive work was done through the monitoring of the joint by a multimethod SHM system incorporating UGW, EMI, AE and EIT methods. It was shown that the co-bonding process reliably works on larger surface areas. Nevertheless, the technique is currently limited to flat bonding areas and further research must be done to transfer it to more complex joint geometries. For the demonstration of the SHM system on component level, a comprehensive measurement data set (US NDE, CT, EIT) was generated, which is also very valuable for future research on advancing damage evaluation methods towards damage localization and quantification. In summary, with the help of the development and exploration of all defined objectives in WP3, a comprehensive structural test including an extensive SHM measurement concept was demonstrated using Demonstrator II.

The last demonstrator III took a stiffened fuselage or wing skin as design reference. It features a single curved skin of constant thickness, on which multiple rows of L-stiffeners were attached through induction welding. L-stiffeners produced from 1st and 2nd life material (KET 3) in different length were successfully welded and showed the scalability of the techniques to larger components. Additionally, the welding of some of the stiffeners were successfully monitored during the process by integrated thermocouples and optical fibres with FBGs (KET 2). The welding of 2nd life materials was challenging because of the non-uniform material characteristics but turned out to be feasible. More temperature data could potentially be of great help in welding 2nd life materials. Optical fibres, which enable the integration and evaluation of several FBGs by employing multiplexing techniques, represent a promising solution.

In conclusion, all demonstrators could transfer technologies developed in WP2 to 4 based on the requirements defined in WP1 to a higher TRL by incorporating the respective KETs in more complex demonstrators than on coupon level. Many technologies performed well. In other cases, room for improvement was discussed as part of a lessons learned approach. For all demonstrated technologies can be concluded that further research must be undertaken to achieve the goal of incorporating the KETs in a certified aircraft component. However, the path to this goal has already been clarified in the context of D6.5, where contributions to standardization were discussed.

REFERENCES

- [1]: A. Degg, C. Kralovec, and M. Schagerl, "Damage monitoring of pinned hybrid composite-titanium joints using direct current electrical resistance measurement". Manuscript submitted for publication.
- [2]: A. Degg, C. Kralovec, and M. Schagerl, "Multi-method structural health monitoring concept for pinned hybrid joints", in Paul Fromme, Zhongqing Su: Health Monitoring of Structural and Biological Systems XVII, vol. 12488, pp. 135-142, 2023
- [3]: A. Degg, C. Kralovec, and M. Schagerl, "Tensile testing of pinned hybrid CFRP/titanium single-lap shear joints and damage monitoring with electrical resistance measurements", in G. Catalanotti, H. Petterman, G. Pittaresi: 9th ECCOMAS Thematic Conference on the Mechanical Response of Composites COMPOSITES 23, DOI: doi.org/10.23967/c.composite.2023.016
- [4]: Haanappel, Sebastiaan Pieter, "Forming of UD fibre reinforced thermoplastics: a critical evaluation of intra-ply shear". PhD Thesis, University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands April 2013